
THE CONTRIBUTION OF YOUTH ASSOCIATIONS TOWARDS COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT IN IGABI LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF KADUNA STATE, NORTH-WESTERN, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The research examined the contributions of youth associations towards community development in Igabi Local Government Area of Kaduna State. A convenience selection of 14 registered youth associations was used in the research which comes from the 14 districts of Igabi Local Government Area and ten respondents were randomly sampled from each of the districts, making a total of 140 respondents constituting the sample size of the study. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data obtained from the questionnaire administered. The research found out that the youth associations helped in the improvement of standard of living of the people in the study area. The study also revealed that the youth associations contributed in political awareness, construction of drainages and culverts and also mobilizes people on the importance of community efforts. The major constraints faced by the youth associations included financial problem and lack of full participation by members. It was recommended that fund raising committees should be created by the youth associations and government should provide assistance to the youth association members as motivation and encouragement measures.

KEYWORDS: Contribution; Youth association; community development; Igabi Local Government; Kaduna State.

INTRODUCTION

Community associations are nongovernmental associations of participating members of a community, such as neighborhood, village, cooperative, or groups of homeowners or property owners in a delineated geographic area (Anon, 2011). Community based organizations otherwise known as local organization have been given different names in different places. These include “community development” associations “neighborhood councils” and united community among others (Agola, 1998). Community based organization is set up by collective efforts of indigenous people of homo or heterogeneous attributes but living or working together within the same environment. Their coming together creates conditions which broadens the base of self governance and diffusion of power through a wider circle of the population (Adeyemo, 2002).

Youth associations and clubs are community based organizations that are formed by youths in a community purposely to contribute towards the betterment of the people and the development of the entire community. These associations could be formal or informal in nature, but often their objectives are the same. Historically, youths input in decision making, problem solving, action and evaluation in communities has received limited attention. However, recent trend indicated that youth associations play an important role in the development of their communities (Musa, 2000). Community development is functional and process oriented and covers a wide field of activities. It emphasizes self-help by citizens and also initiates a people directed process that is based upon their own perception of their needs. It recognizes the necessity for discovering or creating of a community in a process that will utilize the social structure but will help to create new organization and institutions when needed (Ekong, 1988; Abegunde, 2004)

In Nigeria, like other developing countries of the world, youth associations and clubs are equally formed by youth in communities. Youth associations helped in preserving and improving traditions and cultural values of the community; promoting unity and ensuring peace among the people in the community in which they live. They represent their communities and defend its interest in political and developmental issues (Brennan *et al*, 2006; Akinola, 2007). Rural

youths also constitute a strong and very important labour force in development activities of rural communities. Therefore, the youth participation in rural development projects is geared towards bringing an improvement in the standard of living of the people and change in their attitudes, knowledge, behaviors and skills (Odebode, 2000). Moreover, rural youth's participation in rural development projects can increase social responsibility and decrease risky behaviors engaged by the youth (Farinde, 1999). Poor performance of government in meeting the socio economic quest of citizens in the developing countries had been identified as one of the reasons behind the proliferation of community based organizations in the new millennium (Abegunde, 2009). In line with this, many youth associations were formed and have been contributing towards community development in the study area but most of them were not officially registered and no record was established on their level of contribution towards the community development. This research therefore intends to examine the status of the youth associations in terms of official registration with the authorities and their contribution towards development of their community.

RESEARCH METHODS

The Study Area

Igabi Local Government Area is a semi urban area and was carved out of the former Zaria Local Government in 1989. The Local Government Area has fourteen districts and it's geographically located between latitude 9⁰ and 10⁰ North and longitude 6⁰ and 7⁰ East. It is bordered to the west by Ashehu, East by Dan jaba, South by Gadan gayau and Rikoka and North by Jigiro and Juma. Igabi Local Government Area was chosen because of its considerable number of youth associations that actively participated in community development, and most of these youth associations are registered with the Local Government Council.

There are two marked seasons in the area, the dry (windy) season and Rainy (wet) season. The mean annual rainfall is about 1016mm. The area is also characterized by harmattan period between the months of November to February. The area extends from the tropical grassland known as "the guinea savannah" to the "Sudan savannah" with the prevailing vegetation of tall grasses, big trees and shrubs especially in the rainy season.

Sampling procedure and sample size

A sample frame of 14 registered youth associations was used.

These youth associations come from the fourteen districts of Igabi Local Government Area. Simple random sampling technique was used to select both executives and some members of the youth associations (respondents). Ten respondents from each of the fourteen districts were conveniently selected, making a total of 140 respondents constituting the sample size of the study.

Data Collection and analysis

The instrument used for data collection for the research includes structured questionnaire and interview schedule. The questionnaire sort information on Socio-economic characteristics of the respondents, initiatives and objectives of forming community associations, source of finance, self-help project programmes, constraints and possible recommendations. The data collected were subjected to both descriptive and inferential statistics.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Sex

In Table 1, the results on the socio-economic characteristics indicates that most (68.6%) of the respondents were males and 31.5% are females. This revealed that people participate in community development regardless of their gender. This indicates that community development associations traverse culture, language, and are gender neutral as observed by Awotona and Akinola, 1996) but with higher contribution from males. This result is in line with that of Ayanwuyi (2007) who posits that there is no gender bias in community development membership, both gender has their own quota to contribute towards development of their respective community, even though, the males contribute more (due to marriage barriers associated with women who engaged more in house chores).

Age

Table 1 showed that majorities (70%) of the respondents fall within the age range of 21-30 years, 15.7% fall within the age bracket of 31-40 years, and only (14.3%) / were within the age bracket of 18-20 years. This indicates that association members are in their active productive age to participate more in community development programs. This statement is in corroboration with that of Ango (1999) who states that age is one of the factors that determine the effort of an individual in performing assigned functions in community or clubs and societies. Zeldin (2002) further reported that it has been perceived that adolescence stage is a stage of being capable of contributing to the community development by performing well on assigned functions by the community members.

Marital Status

As shown in Table 1, more than fifty-two percent (52.9%) of the respondents are single while 47.1% are married. This indicates that more unmarried people were involved in youth associations than married ones, because the unmarried youths have more time to contribute or work for the association. While some youth marry at early age with consent of their parent, hence family responsibility hindered them from active participation in the association.

Level of Education

Result from Table 1 revealed that 34.3% of the respondents attended secondary school, 28.6% attended Islamic and Arabic school, 18.6% attended tertiary institution, 10% attended adult literary class and only (8.6%) attended primary school. This indicates that most of the rural youth in the study area are educated. This is in accordance with the findings of Hamalai (1999) which posits that basic education gives people access to knowledge, essential skills and new technologies which improve their opportunities in contribution to decision making in communal developments. This is so because education makes a better person out of an individual and increases his or her chances of contributing to the growth of the community.

Primary occupation

Table 1 also indicates that 45.7% of the respondents were traders, 25.7% were civil servants, and others who were either students or housewives constitute 15.7% and 12.9% were farmers respectively. This reveals that traders and civil servants in the study area participate more in youth associations compared to farmers, students or housewives who might be preoccupied in their activities. This finding is in corroboration with Ayanwuyi (2007) who stated that youths are determined to develop their villages due to other economic activities that are available apart from farming. This contradicts findings of Farinde (2000) who posits farming activities as one of the factors that constraint youth participation in community development because the youths work longer hours during the peak of the rainy season and are unemployed during the dry season,

Secondary Occupation

Table 1 further revealed that 41.4% of the respondents had farming as their secondary occupation, 28.6% had trading as their secondary occupation, 11.4% were either students or housewives and 8.6% had civil service as their secondary occupation. This implies that most of the youths in the study area have no any secondary occupation apart from farming. This agreed with the findings of Jibowo (1988) who reported that rural youths, both young males and females between the ages of 15 and 30, depend directly or indirectly on agriculture.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents Socio-economic characteristics (n=140).

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	96	68.06
	Female	44	31.04
Age	18-20 yrs	20	14.03
	21-30 yrs	98	70.00
	31-40 yrs	22	15.07
	40 yrs and above	00	00.00
Marital status	Married	66	47.01
	Single	74	52.09
	Divorced	00	00.00
Level education	Adult education	14	10.00
	Secondary education	48	34.03
	Primary education	12	08.06
	Islamic/Arabic Educ.	40	28.06
	Others (Tertiary Educ.)	26	08.06
Primary occupation	Farming	18	12.09
	Trading	64	45.07
	Civil servant	36	25.07
	Others	22	15.07
Secondary occupation	Farming	58	41.04
	Trading	54	38.06
	Civil servant	12	08.06
	Others	16	11.04

Source: Filed Survey, 2009.

Information of Associations.

Formation of Associations

Table 2 showed that majorities (98.6%) of the associations were formed by community members, and only 1.4% of the associations were formed by the government. This indicates that majority of the members of the association are community members who made decision of forming youth associations which include sport clubs, societies, cooperatives, development associations, religious associations and political groups themselves in the study area, which might be resulted to the fact that they realized the benefit derived from self-help projects to satisfy their development needs. This finding is in corroboration with Kusel (1996), Abegunde,(2004) and Akinola,(2004) their posits that community members are seen as collectivity of people who occupy a given geographical area coming together in an economic and political activity and who essentially constitute a self governing social unit with same common values, experience and feeling of belonging to one another. Also Anyawu (1992) states that development in its own concept is a self-generating process whereby human potentials and relationship are optimized for the purpose of satisfying needs within the context of changing belief and value systems of cultural unit and the large community.

Objectives of forming associations

Table 2 revealed that 67.1% of the youth associations were formed purposely to encourage people to embark on community development projects, 14.3% were formed to strengthen unity among community members, 11.4% were formed to reduce illiteracy among people and 7.1% of the associations were formed to achieve the three objectives of embarking on community development projects, strengthening unity among people and reduce illiteracy among community members. This is in line with Wahab's (2001) observation that people in developing countries have until recently looked up to their government to meet their basic socio-economic demand. This implies that, the key objective of forming youth associations is to move communities forward in terms of development and to encourage people to shoulder most of the community development responsibility themselves in the area, since they can longer depend on government for most of their basic needs. This was also observed by Farinde (1999) that rural youth's participation in rural development projects can increase social responsibility and decrease risky behavior associated with

youths in the urban and semi urban environment. These associations help in engaging the youth's productive time to make a better place to live.

Table 2: Respondents initiatives and objectives of forming community associations (n=140).

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Initiatives of forming associations	Community members.	138	98.06
	Government.	02	01.04
	All of the above.	00	00.00
Objectives of formation of associations	To reduce illiteracy among people.	16	11.04
	To fasten unity among people.	20	14.03
	To encourage people to embark on community development projects.	94	67.01
	All of the above.	10	07.01

Source : Field Survey. 2009.

Source of assistance to associations

Table 3 indicates that most (65.7%) of the associations did not obtain assistance from the government and 34.3% of the respondents were found to obtain assistance from the government. This reveals that most of the expenses incurred during community projects execution are being shouldered by the youth associations. Members contribute and levied themselves for the execution of their outlined budgeted projects annually. While only few associations received assistance from the government in cash and kind for execution of their intended projects, communities in Nigeria and other developing countries lack the basic infrastructural facilities which are ought to have been provided by the government. Thus, for the rural populace to revive their old tradition of collective action and shared strategies to solve problems of infrastructural deprivation they collectively financed their desired projects. Research findings in Nigeria confirmed the achievement of community based institutions in the delivery of essential goods and services (Akinola, 2005). Therefore, government has a vital role to play in community development through encouraging and assisting youth associations which may simplify the task of community infrastructural development. This statement is in accordance with United Nations (1956) which stated that community development is the double aspect of the close collaboration between the local population and the public authorities and creation of condition inducing local population to be optimally self reliant as well as self developing.

Sources of revenue for the associations

Table 3 showed that majorities (77.1%) of the associations generated their revenue through personal contributions, 18.6% generated revenue from wealthy members of the associations and 4.3% generated revenue by both personal contributions and from wealthy community members. This revealed that contribution for community development is the sole responsibility of every member of the society. This result is in agreement with the findings of Ekong (1988) and Divyakirti (2002) who stated that citizens will voluntarily participate or donate in a community activity when they feel obligated to be supportive of that activity.

Association's financial strength

Table 3 indicated that 60% of the respondents had medium financial strength, 22.9% had adequate financial strength, 11.4% had very adequate financial strength and only 5.7% described their financial strength as inadequate. This showed that inadequacy of finance is a factor militating against proper running and execution of community projects. Therefore, government assistance is needed to support the youth associations. This finding is in accordance with National Youth Agency (N. Y. A.) (1999) who called the attention of the government and other non-governmental agencies to come to the aid of youth associations and provide them with the needed capital for the smooth running of their programmes and activities.

Table 3: Respondents receiving of assistance from government, source of revenue and financial strength of Associations (n=140).

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Assistance from government	Yes	48	34.03
	No	92	65.07
Source of revenue of associations	Through personal contribution	108	77.01
	From wealthy members	26	18.06
	All of the above	06	04.03
Financial strength of the associations	Very adequate	16	11.04
	Adequate	32	22.09
	Medium	84	60.00
	Inadequate	08	05.07

Source: Field Survey, 2009.

Participation in Self-help Projects

Tables 4 revealed that majority (85.7%) of the respondents participated fully in self-help projects, while 14.3% were casual participants. This shows that self- help is the only reliable instrument for the people to develop their communities with social infrastructures and therefore, there is need for the members of any community to realize that. This statement is in accordance with Odebode (2000) who reported that youth associations serve as the apex and fulcrum of organizations by which communities can embark on any self-help project. Hitherto the spirit of self-help was relegated to the background; however, the present economic reality in the country has made people find a lasting solution to the socio-economic problems of the country (Akinsorotan and Oludije, 2006). In essence, the whole idea of self-help is to instill in rural people the spirit of wanting to help themselves, thus, killing the syndrome of government will provide and do it all.

Improving the living standard of members

Table 4 also indicated that 42.9% of the associations mobilize people to be conscious of their community, 25.7% organize adult literacy classes, 18.6% provide public lectures on sanitation, and 5.7% engage in mobilization of members on political awareness of their community; organize adult literacy and sanitation classes, and provided public lectures on sanitation as means of improving the living standard of their community. This indicates that development of a community results into improvement of the standard of living of the people in that community. This statement is in corroboration with FAO (1988) which posits that there is need for the youth to participate in development projects because their strength and receptiveness to new ideas through various youth programmes designed to accomplish various social, educational and recreational purposes as a means of improving standard of living in rural areas.

Table 4: Respondents Participation in self- help activities (n=140).

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Participation in self- help	Full participation.	120	85.07
	Casual participation.	20	14.03
	Low participation.	00	00.00
	No participation.	00	00.00
Nature of self-help activity.	By organized adult literacy classes,	36	25.07
	By public lecture on sanitation.	26	18.06
	By mobilization of people to know their right.	60	42.09
	All of the above.	08	05.07

Source: Field Survey, 2009.

Testing of Research Hypothesis

The Chi-square analysis presented in table 5 indicated that organizing literacy classes is not affected by level of participation of youths ($\chi^2 = 0.0160$, $P = 0.8221$). Thus, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected. This could be due to the fact that there are other agencies that provide literacy classes, more so the study area is a semi urban where most youths are schooling. The table also shows that public lecture on sanitation is not influenced by level of participation of youths ($\chi^2 = 0.0310$, $P = 0.8221$). This implies that the null hypothesis is hereby rejected. This could be due to the fact that there are other agencies which provide health talk to the community in general.

In addition, the table indicates that mobilization of people to know their right is not affected by level of participation of youths ($\chi^2 = 0.0537$, $P = 0.8221$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The table further showed that combination of organizing literacy classes, public lecture on sanitation and mobilization of people to know their right is not influenced by the level of participation of youths ($\chi^2 = 0.095$, $P = 0.8221$). This analysis implies that the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, the level of participation of youths association partaking in literacy classes, mobilization of youths, public lecture on health have no influence on programmes of youth associations. This is due to the fact the study area is semi-urban, therefore there a number of agencies that provides such services to the whole community irrespective of age class, association membership and gender.

Table 5: Relationship between level of youth participation and community development (n=140).

Variables	χ^2 Calculated	χ^2 Tabulated	Df	Decision	
Organizing literacy classes	0.0160	0.822NS	4	Reject	H ₀
Public lecture on sanitation	0.0310	0.822S	4	Reject	
Mobilization of people of know their right	0.0537	0.822NS	4	Reject H ₀	
All of the above	0.0951	0.822NS	4	Reject H ₀	

Significant level = 0.05%

Keys

NS = Not Significant at $p > 0.05$, χ^2 = Chi-square value, Df = Degree of Freedom

Constraints and suggestions identified by the respondents

Table 6 showed that majority (87.1%) of the associations faced financial problems, 5.7% of the respondents considered inadequate support from citizens as their problem, while 4.3% of the association members faced both financial and inadequate support problems and 2.9% agreed on lack of full participation of members as their problem. This implies that finance limits youth association programs and activities in community development projects. This indicates that of all the problems faced by youth associations, finance is the most critical. This statement is in line with Odebo (2000) and Akinsorotan and Oludije (2006) they stated that events have shown that there are many factors militating against activities of youth associations which discourage youth involvement in community development projects. Thus, the potential of youths are known to be remarkably under-utilized. The table further indicates that 52.9% of the respondents expressed assistance from government (cash or kind) as the solution to the associations financial problems, while 30% suggested that full participation was the solution, 8.6% declared that assistance from wealthy community members were the solution and 8.6% proposed the combinations of assistance from government, full participation and assistance from wealthy community members could be the remedy to the associations constraints. This implies that assistance from government is needed to gear up the activities of the associations. These findings in accordance with United Nations (1956) which reported that community development is the process by which the effort of people themselves are united with government to improve economic, social and cultural conditions of communities and to enable community members to contribute fully to national development.

Table 6: Respondents suggestions on Problems and the Solutions to the problems of the association (n=140).

Variables	Categories	Frequency	percentage
Problems of the associations	Financial problem.	122	87.14
	Inadequate support from citizens.	08	05.07
	Lack of full participation by members.	04	02.09
	All of the above.	06	04.03
Solutions to the problems	Assistance from government	74	52.09
	Full participation by members	42	30.00
	Assistance from wealthy community members	12	08.06
	All of the above	12	08.06

CONCLUSIONS

It's concluded that youth associations contribute to the infrastructural and standard of living of their communities. It is observed that majority of the youth associations did not obtain any assistance from the government rather contribute funds collectively to execute community projects, consequently these associations had inadequate financial capabilities to handle major development designed by them. Hence Government intervention is needed for maximum performance of the youth potentials.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations deemed necessary:

1. The association members should create fund raising committees so as to tackle the problems of inadequacy of finance.
2. Government should endeavor to assist youth associations as an encouragement and motivation towards community efforts.
3. The association members should be dedicated in participating fully in the activities of the associations.

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Received for Publication: 23/05/2012

Accepted for Publication: 04/07/2012

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